

needles, (70%), m.p. 281° (Found : C, 48.82 ; H, 3.10 ; N, 18.91. $C_9H_7O_4N_3$ requires : C, 48.87 ; H, 3.17 ; N, 19.00%) ; ν_{max} 3 200 (NHNH₂), 1 720 (C=O cyclic), 1 665 (C=O acyclic amido) and 1 095 cm^{-1} (C-O-C) ; δ 2.6 (NH₂), 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH).

For 3–5, R =

a ; *n*-Pr, **b** ; Ph, **c** ; *o*-C₆H₄OH, **d** ; *m*-C₆H₄OH, **e** ; *p*-C₆H₄OH, **f** ; *p*-C₆H₄OCH₃, **g** ; *o*-C₆H₄Cl, **h** ; *p*-C₆H₄Cl, **i** ; *o*-*p*-C₆H₃Cl₂, **j** ; *m*-C₆H₄NO₂, **k** ; *p*-C₆H₄NO₂, **l** ; *p*-C₆H₄NMe₂, **m** ; CH=CHPh, **n** ; 2-furyl, **o** ; CH=CH-CH₃, **p** ; *m*-C₆H₄N.

Scheme 1

4-Arylidenehydrazido-1,4-benzoxazin-2,3-dione (3) :

To a solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was added the respective substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was then distilled off and resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol : **3f**, R=C₆H₄OH (*p*), (70.0%), m.p. 271° (Found : N, 12.32. $C_{17}H_{13}O_5N_3$ requires : N, 12.39%) ; ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 1 760 (C=O lactone), 1 680–1 665br (CONH, C=N) and 1 100 cm^{-1} (C-O-C) ; δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.6 (1H, s, CH=N), 6.8–7.6 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, br s, CONH). For other compounds (yield) and m.p. (°C) are : **3a**, (76), 176 ; **3b**, (73), 159 ; **3c**, (74), 232 ; **3d**, (72), 265 ; **3e**, (73), 241 ; **3g**, (73), 171 ; **3h**, (75), 242 ; **3i**, (76), 123 ; **3j**, (70), 238 ; **3k**, (71), 163 ; **3l**, (70), 226 ; **3m**, (62), 270 ; **3n**, (67), 221 ; **3o**, (70), 149 ; **3p**, (72), 199.

Preparation of 4a–p : To a well-stirred solution of **3** (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.002 mol) in dioxane (dry, 25 ml) was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.002 mol) dropwise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and then refluxed for 3 h. On removal of dioxane under reduced pressure a solid was obtained which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol : **4f**, (65%), m.p. 273° (Found : N, 10.03 ; Cl, 8.50, $C_{19}H_{14}O_6N_3Cl$ requires : N, 10.11 ; Cl, 8.54%) ; ν_{max} 3 300–3 250

(NH), 1 780–1 760 (C=O β -lactam), 1 740 (C=O lactone) and 1 680–1 665 cm^{-1} (CONH) ; δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.45 (1H, d, *J* 9Hz, CH), 6.25 (1H, d, *J* 9Hz, CHCl), 6.8–7.6 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH). For other compounds (yields) and m.p. (°C) are : **4a**, (68), 221 ; **4b**, (63), 258 ; **4c**, (66), 247 ; **4d**, (66), 227 ; **4e**, (67), 260 ; **4g**, (67), 211 ; **4h**, (68), 221 ; **4i**, (64), 187 ; **4j**, (63), 283 ; **4k**, (61), 260 ; **4l**, (65), 289 ; **4m**, (60), 270 ; **4n**, (65), 269 ; **4o**, (62), 251 ; **4p**, (65), 239.

Preparation of 5a–p : Mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) was added to a well-stirred solution of the Schiff base (**3** ; 0.001 mol) in THF (25 ml). The mixture was stirred for 30 min to 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from the proper solvent : **5f**, (64%), m.p. 258° (Found : N, 10.12 ; S, 7.69. $C_{19}H_{15}O_6N_3S$ requires : N, 10.17 ; S, 7.75%) ; ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 1 740 (C=O lactone and 5-membered) and 1 665 cm^{-1} (CONH) ; δ 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.5 (1H, s, CH), 6.8–7.6 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH). For other compounds (yield) and m.p. (°C) are : **5a**, (66), 273 ; **5b**, (69), 263 ; **5c**, (69), 213 ; **5d**, (70), 271 ; **5e**, (68), 262 ; **5g**, (70), 239 ; **5h**, (70), 279 ; **5i**, (70), 167, **5j**, (69), 271 ; **5k**, (67), 247 ; **5l**, (65), 270 ; **5m**, (63), 260 ; **5n**, (70), 257 ; **5o**, (63), 253 ; **5p**, (67), 276.

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Preparation of some 4-Thiazolidinones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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MANY 4-thiazolidinones have been found to possess various pharmacological activities¹. 2,4-Diaminotoluene produces Heinz bodies in the erythrocyte of man and various animals², and it also produces inhibition activity in the growth of Koch

bacillus³. Moreover, the changes in red corpuscles produced *in vitro* by phenylenediamine and 2,4-diaminotoluene can be duplicated *in vivo* in many animals⁴. Keeping this in view, we have studied synthesis (Scheme 1) and antimicrobial activity of some 2,4-bis-[2-substituted-alkyl/aryl-5-H/methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl]-methylphenyls.

(1) X = NH₂

(2) X = N=CHR

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Compound 2 showed a characteristic ir band at 1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N) which disappeared in the ir spectra of 3. Compound 3 showed ir bands at 1640 (O=C-N) and 1140 cm⁻¹ (thiazolidinone ring system); both these bands were absent in the ir spectra of 2. Compound 3 showed characteristic bands at 1370 ν (CH₃), 860 (trisubstituted-benzene ring) and 770 cm⁻¹ (disubstituted-benzene ring). The uv spectra of compound 3 showed bands at 215, 290 and 335 nm.

Compound 3 (R=C₆H₅, R'=H) gave a sharp singlet at δ 2.18 (CH₃), a singlet at δ 2.32 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone ring), a singlet at δ 3.6 (CH of thiazolidinone ring) and a multiplet at δ 7.0-7.8 (ArH).

The above spectral data support the validity of the compounds.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on tlc. The structures were established through their elemental analysis, m.m.p., ir, uv and pmr spectra. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Spectromom-2000 spectrophotometer, uv spectra on a Toshniwal RLD-2 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM-360L spectrometer.

2,4-Bis(phenylamino)methylphenyl (2). Method 1: To 2,4-diaminotoluene (1; 0.05 mol) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 52 ml) was added appropriate aldehyde (0.1 mol) and the contents refluxed for 5 h. Alcohol was then distilled off until the Schiff base commenced to crystallise.

Method 2: A mixture of 2,4-diaminotoluene (0.05 mol), appropriate aldehyde (0.1 mol) and anhydrous ZnCl₂ (0.5 g) was heated on an oil-bath (160°) for 0.5 h, the temperature was raised to 180° for 5 min, then allowed to cool and extracted with CHCl₃. The chloroform was distilled off and the product recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

2,4-Bis(2-substituted-aryl/alkyl/5-H/methyl/4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)methylphenyl (3): To compound 2 (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added thio-glycolic acid or thiolactic acid (0.02 mol) and the content refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. It was then cooled and poured into water. The upper layer was washed with NaHCO₃ solution (10%; 15 ml) and water, dried with Na₂SO₄ and the solvent distilled off at reduced pressure. The residue was recrystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (3)*

Sl. no.	R	R'	M p. °C	Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	H	95-97	65
2.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	H	108	66
3.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	H	123	68
4.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	98	61
5.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	100-02	62
6.	4-N,N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	105	59
7.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	156	62
8.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	138-39	68
9.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	H	110-11	69
10.	C(C ₆ H ₁₁)=CH-C ₆ H ₅	H	110-11	61
11.	5-Br-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	H	119	70
12.	3,5-DiBr-2-OH-C ₆ H ₂	H	198-200	61
13.	C ₄ H ₉ O	H	250d	66
14.	Iso-C ₈ H ₇	H	103	67
15.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	110	63
16.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	95	69
17.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	150d	70
18.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	119	68
19.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	92	66
20.	4-N,N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	152-53	59
21.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	163	63
22.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	123	65
23.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	108-10	66
24.	C(C ₆ H ₁₁)=CH-C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	112-14	64
25.	5-Br-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	CH ₃	101	71
26.	3,5-DiBr-2-OH-C ₆ H ₂	CH ₃	150	70
27.	-C ₄ H ₉ O	CH ₃	153	65
28.	-Iso-C ₈ H ₇	CH ₃	108	62

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

Pharmacological screening: The compounds 3 were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, using cup-plate method⁶, and for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v) and the strain isolated from the sputum of pulmonary tuberculosis patient using absolute concentration method⁶ (Table 1).

All the compounds showed more or less anti-bacterial activity against both the species. But the compounds containing one or more halogen atom were found more active than the others. Replacement of hydrogen by methyl group at the fifth position of thiazolidinone ring increased activity against both the species.

Most of the compounds were found active against both the strains of *M. tuberculosis* at higher concentrations (100 and 150 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). Antitubercular activity of the compounds having hydrogen atom at the fifth position of thiazolidinone ring is nearly the same as the compounds having methyl group at the same position. Most of the compounds are more active against the strain H₃₇R_v than the strain isolated from the sputum of pulmonary tuberculosis patient.

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Biologically Active Thiazolidinone. Part-II. Synthesis and Fungitoxicities of isolated and fused Thiazolidinones derived from Thiosemicarbazones

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IN continuation to the work on thiazolidinones¹, we report here the synthesis and reactions of some new thiazolidinones as well as fungitoxic activity of the new compounds against some fungi. The sequence of reactions leading to the formation of the title compounds is depicted in Schemes 1 and 2.

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Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}/\text{EtOH}/\text{NaOAc}$, (ii) $\text{SHCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}/\text{dry C}_6\text{H}_6$, (iii) K-ferricyanide/NaOH, (iv) $\text{CH}_2\text{CH.NCS}/\text{DMF}$, and (v) concentrated H_2SO_4 .

Scheme 2

A number of thiosemicarbazones (1a-i) and the bis-compound (14) have been prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with aromatic aldehydes.